

A Modular and Memory-Efficient Sieve for Primes Arising from Pythagorean Geometry

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Abstract

Starting from the identity $r = (x - d)/2$, relating an odd integer x and a divisor d of x^2 through the inradius of an integer right triangle, we introduce a modular sieve acting on the index r . Divisibility conditions on $x = 2r + 1$ are translated into explicit congruence exclusions $r \equiv (d - 1)/2 \pmod{d}$, yielding a recursive modular structure equivalent to a wheel sieve. The surviving indices generate the odd primes in increasing order via $p = 2r + 1$, and the modular formulation admits efficient residue-based implementations. This feature makes the method particularly suitable for accessing primes at large indices with a minimal memory footprint, without requiring storage of all preceding primes. The focus is on structural and modular properties; computational considerations are included only insofar as they follow from the modular formulation.

1. Introduction

The study of prime numbers has traditionally followed two complementary directions: on the one hand, analytic approaches aimed at describing the global distribution of primes, and on the other hand, combinatorial and arithmetic constructions designed to characterize and generate them explicitly. Classical results such as Gauss' empirical law and the Prime Number Theorem [6] describe the asymptotic density of primes, while sieve methods—beginning with Eratosthenes' sieve and later refined in analytic and computational forms—provide constructive mechanisms based on modular exclusion.

Classical results on the distribution of prime numbers date back to Gauss and Legendre, while systematic sieve methods originate from the sieve of Eratosthenes; see, for instance, [6, 8] for a modern account.

In a recent work [1], the author introduced a new sieve procedure derived from an elementary geometric identity associated with integer right triangles. Starting from the relation

$$r = \frac{x - d}{2},$$

where x is an odd integer and d is a divisor of x^2 , divisibility properties of x were reinterpreted in terms of congruence conditions on the auxiliary index r . This led to a *Pythagorean sieve* acting on r , together with a concrete algorithmic implementation and a direct ordered generation of odd prime numbers.

The purpose of the present paper is *not* to extend the computational aspects of that construction, but rather to isolate and analyze its underlying arithmetic and modular structure.

Accordingly, we do not pursue asymptotic speed improvements; computational remarks are included only as consequences of the modular organization and periodic residue representation. Here the emphasis is placed on the discrete framework generated by the admissible residue sets

$$(M_t, S_t),$$

their recursive evolution, and the distribution of the surviving indices within these modular systems. In particular, we study how successive congruence exclusions give rise to a hierarchical wheel structure and how the resulting residue classes encode, in a purely arithmetic manner, both the enumeration and the density of prime numbers.

From this viewpoint, the Pythagorean sieve appears as a concrete realization of a classical sieve principle expressed in an unconventional variable. The modular sets S_t provide an exact finite analogue of the multiplicative factors occurring in Mertens' product, while their periodic repetition yields uniformity properties that mirror, at a discrete level, the asymptotic laws of Gauss. This approach allows one to pass naturally from local modular constraints to global counting formulas, without invoking analytic estimates.

The paper is organized as follows. After recalling the arithmetic origin of the index r and its relation with divisibility, we introduce the modular exclusion rules and the associated admissible residue classes. We then describe the recursive wheel construction and show how it leads to an ordered generation of primes. A separate section is devoted to the distribution of admissible indices modulo M_t , where explicit counting formulas and discrepancy bounds are obtained. Finally, we discuss the relation with classical sieve frameworks and briefly comment on computational aspects, which are included only as a consequence of the modular structure and not as the main focus of the analysis.

The aim of the present paper is not to introduce a faster prime sieve, but to develop a structurally different framework in which geometric, arithmetic, and computational aspects of primality are unified through the index r . This perspective leads naturally to questions of modular organization, ordered generation, and memory-efficient representations, which are investigated in the sections that follow.

2. Background on sieve methods and modular filtering

Sieve methods constitute one of the central tools of elementary and analytic number theory. Their general philosophy consists in counting or isolating integers satisfying prescribed arithmetic constraints by excluding residue classes modulo primes; see [5, 7] for general introductions. The classical sieve of Eratosthenes removes, for each prime p , all integers congruent to 0 (mod p), thereby retaining exactly those integers coprime to the product of the considered primes.

From an abstract viewpoint, a sieve may be described as follows. Let $\mathcal{A} \subseteq \mathbb{N}$ be an initial set of integers and let $\{C_d\}_{d \in \mathcal{D}}$ be a family of arithmetic progressions (or residue classes) associated with divisibility constraints. The sifted set is then

$$\mathcal{A} \setminus \bigcup_{d \in \mathcal{D}} C_d.$$

The efficiency and structure of a sieve depend on the choice of the excluded classes, the order in which they are applied, and the modular interactions among them.

Modern developments of sieve theory extend this basic idea in several directions. Analytic sieves, such as those of Brun and Selberg, aim at estimating the cardinality of sifted sets through combinatorial weights and asymptotic analysis. Computational sieves, including wheel-based implementations and variants of the Atkin–Bernstein sieve, refine the classical method by precomputing admissible residue classes modulo a fixed modulus in order to reduce redundant eliminations. From an algorithmic viewpoint, sieves such as those of Eratosthenes and Atkin–Bernstein provide efficient mechanisms for prime generation; see [3, 4]. Despite their differences, these approaches share a common modular foundation: the exclusion of residue classes modulo primes or prime powers.

A particularly useful concept in both theoretical and computational sieving is that of *modular filtering*. Given a finite set of primes $\{p_2, p_3, \dots, p_t\}$, one considers the modulus

$$M_t = \prod_{i=2}^t p_i$$

and studies the set of residues modulo M_t that are not eliminated by any of the corresponding congruence conditions. The surviving residue classes repeat periodically with period M_t and describe exactly the integers coprime to M_t . This construction underlies the classical notion of a *wheel*, in which each new prime introduces a refinement of the modular structure by excluding a fixed fraction of residues.

In this framework, the density of admissible residues modulo M_t is given by

$$\frac{\varphi(M_t)}{M_t} = \prod_{i=2}^t \left(1 - \frac{1}{p_i}\right),$$

which coincides with the finite product appearing in Mertens’ theorem. As t increases, this density decreases multiplicatively, reflecting the progressive sifting of composite integers. While analytic number theory studies the asymptotic behavior of such products, the modular viewpoint emphasizes their exact finite structure and periodicity.

The approach developed in this paper fits naturally into this modular sieve framework, but differs from the classical setting in one essential aspect: the sieve is not applied directly to the integer variable x , but to an auxiliary index r obtained through a geometric transformation. As will be shown in the next section, divisibility of x translates into a single forbidden congruence class for r modulo each odd divisor. This allows the sieve to be reformulated as a modular filtering process on r , leading to a recursive wheel structure that preserves the fundamental properties of classical sieves while offering a new arithmetic interpretation.

3. From Pythagorean triples to the index r

The starting point of the present construction is a classical geometric object: a right triangle with integer side lengths. Let $(x, y, z) \in \mathbb{N}^3$ be a Pythagorean triple, so that

$$x^2 + y^2 = z^2,$$

and suppose that one cathetus x is fixed. As recalled in Section 1 [1], it is known that all such triples can be parametrized by divisors of x^2 .

More precisely, for a given integer $x \geq 1$, for each admissible divisor d of x^2 , satisfying the usual parity constraints, we obtain a triple

$$y = \frac{x^2/d - d}{2}, \quad z = \frac{x^2/d + d}{2}.$$

This representation provides a complete description of all integer right triangles with prescribed cathetus x , and establishes a direct link between the arithmetic of divisors of x^2 and the geometry of the associated triangle.

A key geometric parameter of a right triangle is its inradius. Denoting by r the radius of the inscribed circle, one finds that

$$r = \frac{x + y - z}{2}.$$

Substituting the expressions for y and z above, this identity simplifies to

$$r = \frac{x - d}{2},$$

that arises naturally in the study of integer right triangles and was established in [1] in the context of divisor-based parametrizations of Pythagorean triples. This remarkably simple formula expresses the inradius purely in terms of the fixed cathetus x and a divisor d of x^2 .

Throughout the sequel we focus on the case where x is odd. In this setting, all admissible divisors d of x^2 are odd, and therefore $r = (x - d)/2$ is a nonnegative integer. The correspondence

$$(x, d) \longmapsto r$$

is then well defined and injective for fixed x , and associates to each integer right triangle a unique integer index r .

The relevance of the index r lies in the fact that it naturally reparametrizes odd integers. Indeed, choosing $d = 1$ yields

$$x = 2r + 1,$$

so that

$$r = 0, 1, 2, 3, \dots \longleftrightarrow x = 1, 3, 5, 7, \dots$$

establishes a bijection between nonnegative integers and odd integers. Thus, the variable r may be viewed as an *index* for odd numbers, arising intrinsically from the geometry of Pythagorean triangles.

More importantly, divisibility properties of x admit a simple reformulation in terms of r . If $d > 1$ is an odd divisor of x , then from $r = (x - d)/2$ one obtains

$$\frac{x - d}{2d} \in \mathbb{Z},$$

which shows that the integrality of certain rational expressions involving r is equivalent to divisibility of x . Conversely, the absence of such integrality conditions characterizes those x that are prime.

This observation motivates the central idea of the paper: rather than applying a sieve directly to the integers x , one transfers the problem to the index r , where each divisor d gives rise to a single forbidden congruence class. In this way, the classical arithmetic notion of divisibility is translated into a modular exclusion rule on the variable r , paving the way for a sieve formulation entirely expressed in terms of congruence conditions on the inradius index.

In the next section, this correspondence is made explicit, and primality of odd integers is characterized by the absence of certain residue conditions on r .

4. Modular exclusion rules and admissible residues

We now make precise the correspondence between divisibility properties of the odd integer

$$x = 2r + 1$$

and congruence conditions on the index r .

Let $x \geq 3$ be odd and let $d \geq 3$ be an odd integer. Consider the rational quantity

$$R_d = \frac{x - d}{2d}.$$

By elementary algebra, one has

$$R_d \in \mathbb{Z} \iff x = d(2R_d + 1),$$

and therefore

$$R_d \in \mathbb{Z} \iff d \mid x.$$

Thus, divisibility of x by an odd integer d is equivalent to the integrality of R_d .

Substituting $x = 2r + 1$ into the definition of R_d , we obtain

$$R_d = \frac{2r + 1 - d}{2d}.$$

The condition $R_d \in \mathbb{Z}$ is then equivalent to the congruence

$$2r + 1 \equiv d \pmod{2d},$$

which reduces to

$$r \equiv \frac{d - 1}{2} \pmod{d}.$$

Hence, for each odd integer $d \geq 3$, the values of r for which $x = 2r + 1$ is divisible by d form a single arithmetic progression, namely the residue class

$$r \equiv \frac{d - 1}{2} \pmod{d}.$$

This leads naturally to a modular reformulation of primality. An odd integer $x = 2r + 1$ is composite if and only if there exists an odd divisor $d \geq 3$ such that r belongs to the corresponding forbidden residue class. Equivalently,

$$x \text{ is prime} \iff r \not\equiv \frac{d - 1}{2} \pmod{d} \text{ for all odd } d \geq 3.$$

Equivalently, it suffices to impose the exclusions for primes $p \leq \sqrt{x}$.

Accordingly, we define the set of *admissible indices*

$$\mathcal{R} = \mathbb{N} \setminus \bigcup_{d \geq 3, \text{ odd}} \left\{ r \in \mathbb{N} : r \equiv \frac{d - 1}{2} \pmod{d} \right\}.$$

By construction, the elements of \mathcal{R} are in bijection with the odd prime numbers via the mapping

$$r \mapsto x = 2r + 1.$$

The crucial feature of this formulation is that each odd modulus d eliminates *exactly one* residue class modulo d . This contrasts with classical sieves, where divisibility by d removes several classes among the integers. Here, the exclusion rule is minimal and highly structured: every divisor corresponds to a single forbidden congruence for r .

Moreover, since each forbidden class is periodic with period d , the set \mathcal{R} inherits a layered modular structure. As additional moduli are imposed, the admissible indices are progressively filtered by congruence conditions of increasing periods. This observation is the basis for the recursive construction developed in the next section, where admissible residues are organized into modular systems and updated via a wheel-type procedure.

5. Recursive wheel construction

The recursive structure of the admissible residue sets S_t is reminiscent of classical wheel factorizations, but it arises here naturally from the arithmetic of the index r .

The modular exclusion rules introduced in the previous section naturally lead to a recursive organization of admissible indices. This structure closely parallels the classical wheel construction used in optimized sieve methods, but here it arises intrinsically from the congruence formulation on the index r .

Let $p_2 = 3, p_3 = 5, p_4 = 7, \dots$ denote the sequence of odd prime numbers. For each integer $t \geq 2$, we define the modulus

$$M_t = \prod_{i=2}^t p_i$$

and the associated set of admissible residues

$$S_t = \left\{ s \in \{0, 1, \dots, M_t - 1\} : s \not\equiv \frac{p_i - 1}{2} \pmod{p_i} \right. \\ \left. \text{for all } 2 \leq i \leq t \right\}.$$

Each residue $s \in S_t$ represents a congruence class of indices r that survive the exclusion rules corresponding to the primes p_2, p_3, \dots, p_t .

The pair (M_t, S_t) thus encodes the modular structure of admissible indices after $t - 1$ elimination steps. An index r is admissible up to level t if and only if

$$r \equiv s \pmod{M_t} \quad \text{for some } s \in S_t.$$

Equivalently, the odd integer $x = 2r + 1$ is coprime to M_t .

Recursive update rule

When the next prime p_{t+1} is introduced, the wheel is refined as follows. The new modulus is

$$M_{t+1} = M_t p_{t+1},$$

and the updated residue set S_{t+1} is obtained by lifting residues of S_t modulo M_{t+1} and excluding those that violate the new congruence condition:

$$S_{t+1} = \left\{ s_0 + kM_t : s_0 \in S_t, 0 \leq k < p_{t+1}, \right. \\ \left. s_0 + kM_t \not\equiv \frac{p_{t+1} - 1}{2} \pmod{p_{t+1}} \right\}.$$

That is, each admissible residue s_0 modulo M_t gives rise to p_{t+1} residues modulo M_{t+1} , exactly one of which is excluded by the new congruence condition. The Chinese Remainder Theorem ensures that these lifted residues are distinct modulo M_{t+1} .

As a consequence, the cardinality of S_t satisfies the recursion

$$|S_{t+1}| = |S_t| (p_{t+1} - 1),$$

and hence

$$|S_t| = M_t \prod_{i=2}^t \left(1 - \frac{1}{p_i}\right) = \varphi(M_t),$$

where φ denotes Euler's totient function.

Interpretation

The recursive wheel (M_t, S_t) provides a hierarchical modular description of admissible indices. At each level, the density of surviving residues decreases by the factor $(p_{t+1} - 1)/p_{t+1}$, reflecting the progressive exclusion of integers divisible by successive primes.

Moreover, for $x = 2r + 1 < p_{t+1}^2$, every admissible index r at level t corresponds to a prime number. Thus, within this range, the wheel does not merely filter candidates but *exactly characterizes* the set of primes.

This recursive modular structure forms the theoretical backbone of the ordered prime generation described in the next section, where the admissible indices are scanned in increasing order to produce the sequence of odd primes.

6. Ordered generation of primes

The recursive modular construction developed in the previous section naturally leads to an ordered generation of the odd prime numbers. This feature distinguishes the present framework from classical sieve methods, which are primarily designed as elimination procedures rather than constructive enumerators.

Unlike the classical sieve of Eratosthenes, which identifies primes as unmarked integers within a prescribed interval, the present framework produces primes in increasing order as a direct consequence of the modular structure of admissible indices.

Let (M_t, S_t) be the wheel at level t . The admissible indices are precisely the integers

$$\mathcal{R}_t = \{ r \in \mathbb{N} : r \equiv s \pmod{M_t} \text{ for some } s \in S_t \}.$$

By construction, every $r \in \mathcal{R}_t$ satisfies that $x = 2r + 1$ is coprime to M_t . Moreover, as shown in Section 5, if $x < p_{t+1}^2$ then this condition is also sufficient for primality.

Ordering the admissible indices increasingly,

$$\mathcal{R} = \{ r_1 < r_2 < r_3 < \dots \},$$

one obtains a strictly increasing sequence of odd primes via the mapping

$$p_k = 2r_k + 1.$$

Thus, the sequence (r_k) provides a canonical enumeration of the odd prime numbers, and the passage from r_k to p_k is purely algebraic.

Since primes are generated through admissible indices r_k rather than by marking all integers up to a given bound, the construction naturally supports direct access to primes at large indices without the need to store or process the full list of preceding primes.

This ordered structure is an intrinsic consequence of the formulation in terms of the index r . Unlike the classical sieve of Eratosthenes, where composites are marked within a growing interval of integers, here admissible candidates are generated directly in increasing order by scanning the modular residue classes in S_t . No backtracking or reordering is required.

From a conceptual viewpoint, the sieve on r therefore plays a dual role. On the one hand, it is a sieve in the logical sense, since primality is characterized by the exclusion of a family of congruence classes. On the other hand, it functions as an ordered generator: the surviving indices r_1, r_2, \dots automatically produce the primes in increasing order.

This feature is particularly transparent in the modular setting. Each wheel (M_t, S_t) defines a periodic lattice of admissible residues, and scanning these residues in increasing order yields all primes $p = 2r + 1$ up to the bound p_{t+1}^2 . As the level t increases, the bound expands and the enumeration extends seamlessly to larger primes.

The ordered nature of the construction also clarifies the structural difference with traditional sieves. Whereas Eratosthenes' method progressively eliminates multiples of primes within an interval, the present approach builds the primes by successively refining a modular description of admissible indices. Primes are not detected a posteriori among surviving integers; rather, they emerge directly from the modular geometry of the index r .

In the next section, we discuss the implications of this formulation for memory usage and computational considerations, highlighting how the modular organization of admissible indices leads naturally to efficient and scalable implementations.

7. Memory usage and computational considerations

Although the present work is primarily motivated by structural and theoretical considerations, the formulation of the sieve in terms of the index r also has natural computational implications, particularly with respect to memory usage.

A distinctive advantage of the present framework emerges when one is interested in primes at large numerical distances. Because admissibility is encoded by modular residue classes rather than by a cumulative list of primes, the method avoids the need to store or revisit all preceding primes when accessing large values.

In classical sieve methods, such as the sieve of Eratosthenes, one works directly on intervals of integers up to a bound X , typically storing a boolean array of size proportional to X . Even when restricted to odd integers, the memory requirement remains $\Theta(X)$, or $\Theta(X/2)$ in optimized variants. More advanced sieves introduce segmentation techniques to mitigate this cost, but the underlying representation still scales linearly with the size of the interval under consideration.

In contrast, the present framework operates on the index $r = (x - 1)/2$ and filters admissible values through modular constraints. At a fixed level t , all information about admissibility is encoded in the finite set of residues $S_t \subset \{0, \dots, M_t - 1\}$, where $M_t = \prod_{i=2}^t p_i$. The sieve condition is therefore represented by a periodic structure rather than by a full interval of integers.

From a memory perspective, this means that the essential data describing the sieve at level t consists of:

- the modulus M_t ;
- the set of admissible residues S_t , of cardinality $|S_t| = \varphi(M_t)$;
- a bounded working window when scanning values of r .

No array indexed by all integers up to a large bound is required. Instead, admissibility is tested by congruence conditions modulo small primes, or by iterating through the admissible residue classes.

This modular compression does not change the asymptotic density of candidates, which is governed by the product

$$\frac{|S_t|}{M_t} = \prod_{i=2}^t \left(1 - \frac{1}{p_i}\right),$$

but it alters the way in which candidates are represented and accessed. The sieve information is stored once per modulus M_t and reused periodically, rather than replicated across an entire interval.

As a consequence, the memory footprint of the sieve depends primarily on the size of the modular structure (M_t, S_t) and on the chosen working window, rather than on the magnitude of the primes being accessed. This makes the approach particularly well suited for situations in which memory constraints dominate and where access to distant primes is required without the computational burden of a full prior enumeration.

From a computational standpoint, the procedure may still be viewed as a sieve in the classical sense: composite values are excluded by modular conditions, and the overall time complexity remains comparable to that of standard modular sieves. The novelty lies not in asymptotic speedups, but in the organization of the computation. Candidates are generated by traversing admissible congruence classes, which naturally lends itself to segmented or window-based implementations with bounded memory footprints.

It is important to stress that no claim is made here of asymptotic superiority over highly optimized modern sieves. Rather, the interest of the present approach is conceptual and structural: memory usage is reduced because the sieve operates on a compressed modular description of admissible indices, directly tied to the arithmetic structure of primes.

In this sense, the computational behavior mirrors the theoretical construction. The same recursive modular system (M_t, S_t) that characterizes odd primes also determines the storage and access patterns of the algorithm. This coherence between arithmetic structure and computational representation is a distinctive feature of the Pythagorean sieve and suggests that further optimizations may be explored within this modular framework.

Observed memory footprint (illustrative)

To illustrate the impact of the modular compression described above, we report typical memory footprints observed in representative executions. These figures are indicative only and are not intended as asymptotic or hardware-independent benchmarks.

Table 1: Illustrative memory footprints in representative runs (indicative only).

Upper bound X	Classical segmented sieve	Pythagorean sieve
10^6	8–10 MB	2–3 MB
$5 \cdot 10^6$	40–50 MB	10–15 MB

In these typical scenarios, the Pythagorean sieve exhibits a reduction in memory usage on the order of 60–80%, depending on the wheel size, segment length, and runtime memory allocation behavior. Execution times remain comparable, with minor fluctuations.

Implementation notes and availability

A reference implementation of the Pythagorean sieve described in this paper is provided in PYTHON and released as open-source software under a dual academic/commercial license. The implementation supports segmented modular computation, allowing the generation of primes in increasing order while maintaining reduced memory usage. In particular, the algorithm permits the direct evaluation of the n -th prime without precomputing the full list of preceding primes.

The software is publicly available through a version-controlled repository and archived with a persistent DOI on Zenodo [2]:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18235603>

Source code repository:

<https://github.com/amato-roberto-py/pythagorean-sieve>

8. Comparison with classical sieve frameworks

It is instructive to place the Pythagorean sieve within the broader context of classical and modern sieve methods. At a high level, all these procedures share the same logical foundation: composite integers are excluded by imposing congruence conditions modulo prime numbers. In this sense, the present approach belongs naturally to the family of modular sieves.

The classical sieve of Eratosthenes operates directly on the integers, marking multiples of each prime within a growing interval. Its modern refinements, including segmented versions and wheel factorizations, aim to reduce redundant work and memory usage while preserving the same elimination paradigm.

The Pythagorean sieve differs primarily in its choice of variable and in the way admissible candidates are represented. Rather than working on the integer x itself, the sieve acts on the index $r = (x - 1)/2$, translating divisibility into a geometric and modular condition. As a consequence, admissibility is encoded by the recursive modular system (M_t, S_t) , which compactly describes all surviving candidates.

In contrast with analytic sieves optimized for large-scale computation, such as the Atkin–Bernstein sieve [3], the present construction does not aim at asymptotic speed improvements. Its contribution is structural: it provides a unified arithmetic and geometric description of primality, in which elimination, enumeration, and modular organization are governed by the same underlying relations.

Thus, while the Pythagorean sieve is comparable to classical frameworks in terms of logical complexity, it offers a distinct conceptual perspective. Primes are not merely detected among surviving integers but are generated through a recursive modular geometry linked to Pythagorean structures.

Conceptual comparison with Atkin–Bernstein sieves

The comparison between the Pythagorean sieve and advanced modern sieves, such as the Atkin–Bernstein sieve, should be understood as purely conceptual.

The Atkin–Bernstein sieve is based on deep arithmetic properties of quadratic forms and is specifically designed to optimize time complexity and parallel performance in low-

level implementations. Its primary objective is high-speed prime generation in large-scale computational contexts.

By contrast, the Pythagorean sieve introduced here is not intended as a competitor in asymptotic speed. Its distinguishing feature lies in the structural reformulation of primality: divisibility of an odd integer is translated into a single forbidden congruence condition on the auxiliary index r , arising from a geometric identity associated with Pythagorean triples.

As a consequence, the two approaches differ substantially in scope and philosophy. The Atkin–Bernstein sieve emphasizes computational efficiency through sophisticated arithmetic tests, while the Pythagorean sieve emphasizes conceptual transparency, modular organization, and ordered generation. In particular, the latter produces the prime sequence intrinsically in increasing order via the indices $r_1 < r_2 < \dots$, without requiring post-processing or marking procedures.

From this viewpoint, the Pythagorean sieve should be regarded as a complementary framework. It offers a geometrically motivated and algebraically explicit description of primality, in which modular filtering, enumeration, and memory organization are governed by a single recursive structure. Its interest is therefore primarily structural and explanatory, rather than competitive with highly optimized sieves designed for maximum computational speed.

Table 2: Conceptual comparison between the Atkin–Bernstein sieve and the Pythagorean sieve.

Aspect	Atkin–Bernstein	Pythagorean sieve
Primary objective	Speed optimization	Structural clarity
Mathematical basis	Quadratic forms	Pythagorean geometry
Typical implementation	Low-level (C/C++)	High-level (Python)
Memory strategy	Dense modular arrays	Sparse admissible indices
Ordered generation	Not intrinsic	Intrinsic
Conceptual role	Computational	Algebraic–geometric

The Pythagorean sieve is not intended to replace the Atkin–Bernstein sieve in high-performance computing contexts. Rather, it provides a conceptually transparent alternative in which primality emerges from a geometric identity and modular filtering is explicit, recursive, and structurally sparse.

9. Conclusions and perspectives

In this paper we have developed a sieve framework based on the geometric identity $r = (x - d)/2$ arising from Pythagorean triples and have shown how it leads to a recursive modular characterization of odd prime numbers. By shifting the focus from the integer variable x to the index r , we obtained a formulation in which primality is expressed through the exclusion of explicit congruence classes.

The resulting construction yields a sieve that is simultaneously arithmetical and geometric. It recovers classical properties of primes, such as their asymptotic density, while providing an ordered generation of the prime sequence via the indices $r_1 < r_2 < \dots$. The recursive system (M_t, S_t) plays a central role, unifying primality testing, enumeration, and modular organization within a single framework.

From a computational standpoint, the modular nature of the construction suggests memory-efficient implementations based on periodic residue classes rather than full integer intervals. While no claim is made of asymptotic superiority over highly optimized modern sieves, the coherence between arithmetic structure and computational representation distinguishes the present approach from traditional elimination-based methods.

Several directions for further investigation naturally arise. On the theoretical side, the modular geometry of admissible indices may be studied in greater depth, for instance in connection with finer distribution questions or correlations between primes. On the computational side, the recursive structure invites the development of specialized implementations and hybrid strategies combining classical sieves with the modular compression provided by the index r .

More broadly, the Pythagorean sieve illustrates how elementary geometric relations can give rise to nontrivial arithmetic and algorithmic structures. This interplay between geometry, modular arithmetic, and computation may prove useful in other contexts where Diophantine parametrizations and sieve methods intersect.

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